

PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS AND CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14967594>

***Abstract.** Health is one of the most important components of human maturity and a guarantee of the inviolable human right to self-development, active participation in personal and social life. In our society, human health, physical fitness, culture of a healthy lifestyle are very important social values. Ensuring the health of the nation, maintaining the gene pool of people will be resolved quite positively only through a healthy lifestyle. This means that all social institutions of society; families, educational institutions, districts and independent education are faced with the task of explaining to the citizens of our society the content and essence of a healthy lifestyle, educating young people as alert, knowledgeable and versatile individuals. This article is written about the creation of pedagogical conditions for the formation of a healthy lifestyle for young people.*

***Keywords:** healthy lifestyle, pedagogical problem, youth, health.*

INTRODUCTION

The changes taking place in the socio-political and economic life of modern society present qualitatively new requirements for the upbringing of modern youth. Environmental and social upheavals, instability of life, strengthening of technocratism and lack of spirituality, changes in traditional foundations and moral guidelines create a real humanistic crisis of society. This crisis manifests itself as a social protest, an increase in crime, drug addiction, alcoholism among adolescents.

Despite the unfavorable conditions created for the formation and development of modern youth, the state of health of the younger generation is alarming. In this regard, the increased interest in health problems in Uzbekistan on the part of not only medical workers, but also the entire population is fully justified. Attention to the health problem is increasing every year, both in our country and around the world. In developed foreign countries, health problems, as well as the level and quality of life, are part of national security, as evidenced by state health programs and national health information surveys. Their implementation is possible because it is realized that the degree of health directly depends on the attitude towards it at the state and personal level. There are facts from world practice about a decrease in the growth of cardiovascular and oncological diseases (USA), tobacco addiction and a decrease in alcohol consumption (Finland), a decrease in the growth of crime and the number of abortions (Netherlands, Sweden), due to the formation of proper motivation for a healthy lifestyle.

These circumstances allow us to assert that the formation of a healthy lifestyle (HLS) as a technology for maintaining health and ensuring high efficiency and productivity of human labor is the most important problem of modern science and practice.

PURPOSE OF WORK

The purpose of this article is to analyze and identify the problems of forming and developing a healthy lifestyle for future doctors. Find ways to solve them, develop conclusions and recommendations on a healthy lifestyle for medical students.

METHODS

The purpose of the study was to analyze the formation and development of the lifestyle of medical students in order to make practical recommendations on the formation of the need for a healthy lifestyle in order to preserve and strengthen health. The analysis of educational and sociocultural trends made by scientists shows that various aspects of human behavior in relation to their health in the last decade have become the subject of interdisciplinary research and the object of close attention of society.

DISCUSSION

According to M. Deryugina, there are several directions in the study of this problem: psychological and pedagogical, philosophical and sociological, medical and hygienic.

Researches of scientists in the field of pedagogy and psychology indicate that the most favorable opportunities for personality development exist during the period of its formation (P.P. Blonsky, L.S.Vygotsky, I.S. Kon, B.T. Likhachev, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, K. D. Ushinsky, S. T. Shatsky, D.B. Elkonin). It was at this time that the foundations of the future life position of a person were laid, therefore the main role in the formation of value orientations was assigned to the education system.

According to the prevailing opinion, the educational process in an educational institution should include two leading areas of organizational and pedagogical activity in the formation of a healthy lifestyle:

- creation of optimal conditions for the internal environment - microsocial (humanistic relations, a favorable psychological climate, an active creative environment), through joint activities and communication of students and teachers in the educational process (Yu.K. Babansky, B.S. Gershunsky, V.I. Zvereva, A.V. Mudrik and others);

- providing social and pedagogical conditions (attitudes, needs, abilities) for self-development and self-education of students through the mechanisms of self-knowledge, reflection, goal-setting (B.G. Ananiev, L.I.Bozhovich, T.M. Davydenko, B.D. Parygin, S.L. Rubinstein, V.A. Yakunin and others). In this article methods of statistics, comparative analysis, work with documents, questionnaires were used.

Health is one of the highest human values. Health is a state of complete well-being that includes the following components:

- high efficiency, resistance to diseases;
- self-confidence, based on the ability to manage your feelings and thoughts;
- the desire and ability to manage their own health and build their behavior without prejudice to the well-being of others.

Researchers consider a healthy lifestyle to be the most important factor in maintaining and strengthening health. A healthy lifestyle is an individual system of human behavior that ensures physical, mental and social well-being in a real environment and active longevity [16]. Analysis of scientific literature shows that the formation of a healthy lifestyle is associated with education and pedagogy. In a broad sense, physical culture education is understood by scientists, teachers, and cultural studies as a way of introducing a person to physical culture. Historical analysis of the

problem of forming a healthy lifestyle of students through education has shown that this issue is relevant throughout the formation and development of pedagogical science. Outstanding teachers, philosophers, scientists [13, 6, 4, 2] expressed ideas about the means of preserving and strengthening health, they identified the conditions necessary for the upbringing of a harmonious, healthy personality. Solving the problem of the health of students is a priority of the educational system, since, according to modern concepts, the main importance in the formation, preservation and strengthening of the health of an individual is his/her indifferent attitude to his/her own health. This presupposes the formation of a person's life priority of health and is the most important task of education. In this process, the priority role is given to teachers, because in terms of their social status and professional status, they are not only carriers of social knowledge, but also the embodiment of moral norms, patterns of behavior, a healthy lifestyle and an adequate attitude to their health. They are always active, creative individuals.

A healthy lifestyle (HLS) is a process of forming a versatile personality capable of working actively, living in a creative environment, easily enduring strong physical and mental stress, extremely dangerous and harmful factors of influence [1].

In the literature on philosophy and social hygiene, much attention has recently been paid to the problems of forming a healthy lifestyle. The socio-psychological, medico-hygienic, economic, motivational aspects of the personality are studied. However, methodological problems and socio-hygienic criteria for a healthy lifestyle, the specificity of some regions, climatic and geographical conditions, ethnic features of the culture of life of the population have not been sufficiently studied.

The model of the national concept of healthy lifestyle formation allows the process of healthy lifestyle formation among the population of the republic in a certain order and on a scientific basis, and increases its efficiency. People will have the opportunity to compare their existing lifestyle, hygiene behavior, and medical culture and activities in the community with the model stage and make appropriate changes.

If we talk about the role of a motivating factor in the formation of a healthy lifestyle, then, first of all, the term motivation, in essence, is to motivate a person to start a certain activity, justify and explain its importance. In particular, the motivating factor in the problem of the formation of a healthy lifestyle is explaining to people why they should live in a healthy lifestyle, why they should not choose an unhealthy lifestyle. [2].

When assessing the role of the motivational factor in the process of forming a healthy lifestyle among the population, it is necessary to pay attention to the presence of three basic elements in each person, which are necessary for the analysis of his daily life. Including in each person:

- Knowledge of a healthy lifestyle;
- Firm belief that a healthy lifestyle can make a person healthy and prolong life;
- Having a serious desire for a healthy lifestyle.

In theory, in the daily life of people, this triangle can take different forms. The internal need of each person to improve health determines his practical actions in this direction. Accordingly, all factors:

- lead a hygienically correct and reasonable way of life, i.e. healthy lifestyle;
- can be divided into those who lead unsanitary, i.e. unhealthy Lifestyle. [four].

In the current period of the growing and developing socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is very important to clearly define the socio-hygienic criteria for a healthy lifestyle.

The ideology of a healthy lifestyle in our country is not a collection of laws and knowledge about human health, but a system of views on strengthening human health. According to R.U. Arzikulov, the ideology of a healthy lifestyle should include a philosophy of a lifestyle, state policy on the formation of a healthy lifestyle, legal and moral foundations of a healthy lifestyle, pedagogy, psychology, sociological culture, ethics and integrity of a healthy lifestyle [8].

It is known that a criterion is such a dimension with which we can compare the processes that we need to measure with the formed standard, we can evaluate it. When measuring complex social processes, such as a healthy lifestyle, it is important to formulate measurements that are acceptable and necessary for us.

Criteria that can be used to measure a healthy lifestyle include:

- Be active in social and labor processes, engage in effective creative activity;
- Exemplary life in the family and in everyday life;
- Striving to realize their physical and mental abilities;
- Live in harmony with the natural and social environment;
- Striving to gradually develop your personality in order to become a healthy and versatile person;
- Strive to protect yourself from the enslavement of bad habits of an unhealthy lifestyle and from falling into the whirlpool of life;
 - The desire to live a contented life, not only because he lives a long time, but also because he lives a good life;
 - Valuable qualities and characteristics, such as a healthy lifestyle, can be included that will accompany him throughout his life.

Everyone needs to regularly strengthen their body parts to increase their reserve capacity. To build up health reserves, it is recommended to adhere to the following rules of a healthy lifestyle:

- Regular physical education and physical labor. Exercise at least 6 hours a week;
- Work with normal mental and physical stress, active rest after intense mental work. Modern and meaningful organization of work and leisure;
 - Rational and balanced nutrition, weight loss, limiting the consumption of animal fats, sugar and sweets;
 - To refuse from bad habits;
 - Body hardening;
 - Stay in the fresh air for at least 2-3 hours every day;
 - Strict adherence to the schedule, sleep at least 8 hours a day;
 - Change your lifestyle and work if necessary;
 - marriage, study and job satisfaction. [one].

To increase the reserve capacity of the body, it is necessary to achieve a gradual organization, not a waterfall. These include forcing the heart and body muscles to work with various physical exercises, doing these exercises at the same time and following a certain routine, creating a habit of alternating mental and physical work, etc.

It is known that, fighting for the future of our generation - a healthy generation, we will have to teach the nation to lead a healthy lifestyle in order to achieve our goal. When we talk about a healthy generation, we must have in mind not only physically strong children, but also a spiritually rich and healthy generation. After all, it is impossible to be physically healthy without being spiritually healthy. Both concepts are compatible and require one from the other. And it is impossible to break a nation with a physically and spiritually healthy generation. Since our main goal is to form a physically healthy, highly spiritual nation, united on the basis of a single national idea, we must teach it to lead a healthy lifestyle.

Today the problem of a healthy lifestyle is the most important problem of mankind. And the formation of a scientifically grounded, socially and hygienically rational way of life, contributing to the full development of the individual, work, life and rest, scientifically grounded social and hygienic activities are a necessity.

The promotion of a healthy lifestyle in the education system should be carried out sequentially in different directions, on the basis of a specific program, in specific areas. In particular, propaganda should be aimed at providing students with certain medical and hygienic knowledge about a healthy lifestyle in the process of higher pedagogical education, to form their understanding of the influence of a healthy lifestyle on the development of the human body, developing skills to make the health of others a daily habit. In addition, it is necessary to widely promote a healthy lifestyle in the media, as well as deeply integrate it into the educational programs of schools, lyceums and colleges in conjunction with all educational institutions.

Traditionally, in the Uzbek family, signs of a centuries-old affiliation are clearly expressed. The elders in the family - grandparents, close relatives, neighbors, makhalla - are directly involved in the formation of healthy ideas and knowledge in the minds of children. According to our mentality, the influence of grandparents, neighbors and relatives on the upbringing of our children is stronger than the influence of parents. They define the spiritual environment in the family. This tradition of upbringing is an important spiritual and pedagogical value left over from the past, and in the life of our great ancestors, this style of upbringing was formed and reached a certain systemic level.

Under the influence of certain events and various changes that occur in life, a person's lifestyle is formed. As society develops, an increase in the flow of information, an increase in demand for a dynamic lifestyle, interaction and communication become more complex, affect the psyche of students. As a result, they are increasingly responsible for choosing a set of behaviors based on their destiny, family, community, lifestyle, and the pursuit of mental, emotional and freedom. This lifestyle often requires the prevention of various neurological disorders that may occur in students and adolescents. Achieving this goal requires, first of all, the organization of a healthy lifestyle on a personal and social scale, as well as the implementation of important directions to achieve its continuity. To do this, you need to understand the essence of the problem and know how to solve it. And in the system of continuous education, it is necessary to create appropriate conditions for the formation of a healthy lifestyle for students.

Formation of a healthy lifestyle as a pedagogical problem. The socio-political and economic transformations taking place in our country have put teachers in front of an urgent need to revise pedagogical positions, to critically re-evaluate the established scientific, theoretical and practical systems of education and training of qualified personnel. The changes primarily concern the rethinking of the goals, content, forms, methods and structure of education.

By the end of the 20th century, the evolution of knowledge, the deep differentiation of sciences brought forward the integral problem of man among the topical ones. This problem becomes, in fact, common both for the entire science as a whole and for its individual branches, including precise and technical ones.

The methodologist of pedagogical science VS Shubinsky in his works claims that in our time "the paradigm of the main goal of education is fundamentally changing: it becomes not a person, but a person in multidimensional (including personal) characteristics of existence" [15].

Modern pedagogy must find adequate ways to involve the younger generation in maintaining their health. International experience shows that health programs aimed at adolescents are the most promising. In world science, it is proved that preventive programs are incomparably more profitable than programs to combat the consequences of inadequate health of the population. An economic analysis carried out in developed countries showed that the introduction of health protection and promotion programs during the formation of an individual would provide an effective ratio of the cost of costs and benefits received as 1:14, which is a very high indicator [8].

However, the teaching staff of educational institutions are still not involved in the development of the necessary programs and concepts of student health. This leads to the fact that the task of preventing and preserving the health of students in educational institutions is considered secondary in relation to the basic educational process, which sharply reduces the effectiveness of work to preserve and strengthen the health of students and teachers.

It can be stated that, firstly, work to preserve health in educational institutions, as a rule, has a purely medical basis, because proceeds from the idea of "curing diseases"; secondly, the technologies of transferring knowledge about health and a healthy lifestyle to the behavioral level have not been developed by pedagogical theory and practice; thirdly, there are no convincing criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the process of health improvement of students, despite the fact that their health tends to deteriorate [8].

The leading reasons that adversely affect not only the physical, but also the mental health of students in educational institutions are hypokinesia (insufficient physical activity), inability to cope with the training load, malnutrition, violation of work and rest, failure to comply with a number of hygienic requirements (ventilation, illumination of educational places, furniture inadequacy, etc.), non-observance of safety rules, lack of knowledge about health and a healthy lifestyle among teachers, parents and students [3, 5, 11, 12, 1].

Scientists point out that the main source of mental health disorders in adolescents is educational overload, which occurs due to the overload of programs with background information, a large number of subjects studied and the inability of young people to learn. In addition, the clearly expressed discrepancy between the external requirements and the psychophysical capabilities of future specialists, the discrepancy between the manifestations of the individual properties of the nervous system and the requirements of educational activity, lead to large losses of health [2, 4, 14, 7].

The education system cannot be considered humanistic if the values of health have not found their proper place [6]. The need to eliminate the contradiction associated with the lack of demand for a huge scientific potential for solving the problems of humanizing the educational process led to the emergence of a new integrative science - valeology, located at the junction of pedagogy and medicine, philosophy and psychology, ethics and physical culture, which has received recognition, but also causes some more, ambiguous statements [10, 9, 13].

Creation of pedagogical conditions for the formation of a healthy lifestyle for students. In M. Deryugina's understanding, "conditions" are a set of circumstances, that is, what makes it possible and necessary for a certain consequence to appear. In this case, the cause determines the effect, and other conditions play not a necessary, but secondary role. Organizational and pedagogical conditions significantly affect the final result of training and education [1].

The processes taking place today in education and contributing to the construction of a health, educational system (humanization, differentiation, psychologization) must have a certain structure and obey its laws. The consistency, cooperation and rhythm of the joint work of teachers, students, heads of educational institutions and parents is a real step towards the humanization of the educational system and contributes to the overall solution of the problem of the formation of healthy lifestyles of students in the process of education.

RESULTS

The basic principles on which the work of educational institutions should be based are presented in the special scientific literature. It is:

- The principle of conformity to nature, refusal to "remake" a young man. Personality upbringing, taking into account the existing potential, based on the laws of internal development, search, detection and strengthening of internal forces;
 - The principle of the continuity of the process of personality development, provided by the mechanism of continuity between goals, content, forms and methods, the nature of pedagogical interaction, valeologization of the pedagogical process and technologies for the development of physical and spiritual culture of the individual;
 - The principle of the integrity of the development process, involving the coverage of the emotional-sensual, cognitive and volitional spheres of the individual, in which general and special knowledge and skills allow the individual to realize the benefits of a healthy lifestyle;
 - The principle of the personality-oriented nature of the system, implemented through the goals of improving the health of each student, individualizing the content, forms, methods and pedagogical means of achieving health;
 - The principle of integration of lifelong learning healthy lifestyles with science, nature, practical activities of man and society;
 - The principle of self-organization and self-development through the choice of meaning and life orientations, the consistent passage of the stages of self-knowledge, self-determination and self-realization, through the accumulation of personal experience of introspection, self-control, self-correction in the process of development and organization of the system of pedagogical support for the development of stable healthy lifestyle habits by future specialists [1].
- The development of a healthy lifestyle formation system involves:
- The choice of goal-setting, a new understanding of the goal of education and upbringing
 - as a young person's self-realization of his strengths and abilities in a healthy lifestyle
 - Development of a new content of training and education based on the recognition of the priority of the value of health for individuals and society, valeologization of the content of education and the pedagogical process as a whole;
 - Correction of the educational process, taking into account the state of health of students, factors and conditions for the formation of healthy lifestyles of the younger generation;

- Staffing of pedagogical activities, professional development of teachers and masters of industrial training based on the principles of integrativity, interrelation, interdependence of information from the field of pedagogy, psychology, medicine, sociology, ecology;
- Coordination of the activities of pedagogical and medical workers, parents, students, focused on solving the problems of training, education and development of future specialists, depending on their individual abilities, physical and mental health, moral well-being.

CONCLUSION

Among the numerous problems facing the school and pedagogical science, the problem of forming a healthy lifestyle for students, which has not yet received the necessary scientific substantiation, is of particular relevance. At the same time, the practice of the educational process in educational institutions shows that the lack of knowledge on this issue complicates the improvement of the educational process, does not allow future employees to develop responsibility for maintaining their own health.

Preserving and strengthening the health of students is a complex social and pedagogical problem. First of all, it requires a reorientation of the goals of education and upbringing. If one of the life values of a modern worker should be his health, then, of course, one of the priorities of modern education should include the formation of a healthy lifestyle for students.

The vital activity of students in educational institutions is due to a multifactorial impact. We have identified and considered these factors, their implementation in social institutions for the formation of a healthy lifestyle (family, educational institution, environment, health care) and means (training, communication, play activities, socially useful work) that constitute the essence of the process of socialization of a student when he is formed as a person and a competitive employee.

Analysis of the influence of the selected factors on the formation of a healthy lifestyle in the younger generation allows us to conclude that educational institutions can influence this process through the system of organized education and upbringing, setting it in an appropriate direction.

The main organizational and pedagogical conditions for resolving the tasks set for the education system is to improve work with students, pedagogical and medical personnel, parents, and various social institutions. This becomes possible on the basis of a systematic, comprehensive study and accounting of the state of health of students, corresponding to the orientation of the educational process; selection of content, methods and forms of education, corresponding to the formation of a healthy lifestyle as the goal of education.

This holistic multidimensional process requires the training of teachers who are aware of the priority value of students' health as a necessary condition for their life and the realization of all the potential and creative possibilities of the individual.

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